

Research Article

Contraceptive potential of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (Linn.)- An update

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ABSTRACT

The use of plants and plant preparations as contraceptives in family planning may play a critical role in population regulation since the herbal products are cheap and have a natural origin with higher safety margins and lesser or no side effects. Further, it allows couples to control their fertility without consulting a health worker. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (Linn.) belongs to family Malvaceae and is a world-wide evergreen ornamental shrub in gardens. Though, each and every part of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* has various pharmacological properties, the extracts of flower exhibit remarkable contraceptive properties in both males and females as reported by researchers. It is possible that, given research attention, products from this plant could come into widespread use for the reduction of unwanted pregnancies. This article focuses mainly on the contraceptive potential of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* so as to promote the research on this plant.

Keywords: Contraceptive; Herbal; Antispermatic; Fertility; Postcoital; Pharmacological.

INTRODUCTION

The one of the most serious problems in developing countries like India is the geometrical increase in human population that can be resolved only by effective family planning methods. Though, there are several approaches available for control of fertility in men and women, no one has emerged as the best choice free from unwanted side-effects. The adverse effects caused by contraceptive pills and injectables include increased blood transaminase and cholesterol levels, indigestion, weight gain, headache, depression, fatigue, hypermenorrhea and intermenstrual bleeding. In addition, being hormones, these also disturb the metabolism of lipid, protein, carbohydrates, enzymes and vitamins [1]. The Indian ancient texts, the Rig Veda, Charaka Samhita and Shushruta Samhita describe a large number of plants, some of which enhance reproductive processes while others hinder reproductive functions [2]. Therefore, in recent years, much attention has been focused on indigenous medicinal plants for possible contraceptive effect in human, since herbal preparations are easily available, cheap, have a natural origin with higher safety margins, and cause lesser or no side effects [3]. Further, an oral herbal contraceptive allows couples to control their fertility without consulting a health worker, which in turn would likely markedly increase the number of couples practicing family planning [4]. Plants exhibit contraceptive and abortifacient properties through rapid expulsion of the fertilized ova from the fallopian tube, inhibition of implantation due to a disturbance in estrogen-progesterone balance, fetal abortion perhaps due to lack of supply of nutrients to the uterus and the embryo, and also on the male side through affecting sperm count, motility and viability [5]. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (Linn.) belongs to family Malvaceae and grows as an evergreen herbaceous ornamental shrub throughout the world. *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* (*H. rosa-sinensis*) is native to tropical and sub-

tropical regions and is widely grown in Indian gardens. It bears large flowers on the bushy hedges which are usually dark red in color with no aroma. The beautiful flowers of the plant carry several common names such as China rose (English), Jasum (Hindi), Japa (Sanskrit) etc. It is well established that the leaves, stems, roots and flowers of *H. rosa-sinensis* have various pharmacological properties. The extracts predominantly prepared from *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers show remarkable anti-fertility properties in both males and females. Kholkute and co-workers [6] prepared hot benzene extracts from flowers, leaves, and stem barks of *H. rosa-sinensis*, collected during winter, spring, rainy and summer seasons, to evaluate the postcoital antifertility potential of the plant. They found that only extracts from the flowers of the plant were 100% effective in preventing pregnancy. Further, flowers collected during the winter showed the greatest potency, followed by those collected in the spring, rainy season, and summer, in decreasing order. The present article focuses on the contraceptive potential of *H. rosa-sinensis* so as to draw attention of researchers to this plant for evaluation as a herbal contraceptive.

TRADITIONAL VALUES AS REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH CARE

In the ancient system of medicine, flowers of *H. rosa-sinensis* have been described to be used in various ways to treat a number of reproductive problems. *H. rosa-sinensis*, the Japa flowers, crushed with sour gruel followed by jaggery, were prescribed as a contraceptive in ancient literature (Bhaavaprakasha). Flower buds were used in "Garbha Anaasthaapaka Yoga" for contraception. For leucorrhoea and other gynecological disorders, 10-12 buds of Japaa flowers minced with milk were very effective, and in amenorrhoea, Japaa flowers and Jyotishmati (*Celastrus paniculatus*) leaves crushed with sour gruel, were administered (Chakradatta) for cure. In folk medicine,

flowers crushed with sugar added to the fresh juice, were given for controlling excessive uterine bleeding. Flowers, fried in clarified butter, were also given in menorrhagia. Leaves and stems of *H. rosa-sinensis* were also used for abortion. *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers have been used for reproductive health care in different countries of the world. In China, flowers of the plant are useful in emmenagogue; In India, these are used for controlling fertility in males and females; in Peru, these are popular for their contraceptive properties in males; in Hawaii, these are used to improve lactation; in Bangladesh, these are used to control the menstrual cycle, and in Cook Islands these are helpful to cure gonorrhoea.

REPRODUCTIVE EFFECTS OF *HIBISCUS ROSA-SINENSIS*

Antispermatic and androgenic activities

Kholkute [7] first reported the effect of the flower extract of *H. rosa-sinensis* on spermatogenesis and accessory reproductive organs in rats. In another study, oral intake of benzene, chloroform and alcoholic extracts (125 and 250 mg/kg body weight for 20 days) of *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers led to decreased spermatogenic elements of testis and epididymal sperm count in albino mice. Further, researchers reported the androgenic activity of the plant extract due to increase in the weight of accessory reproductive organs [8]. Olagbende *et al.* [9] also reported the anabolic effect of leaf extracts of *H. rosa-sinensis* in immature albino male rats. Our study with *H. rosa-sinensis* has also shown that treatment with benzene extract of leaves of this plant at 200 mg/kg body weight for 35 days results in complete suppression of spermatogenesis in testis and fertility of males, and a remarkable implantation failure in impregnated female albino mice (an unpublished data).

Antiovarian and antiestrogenic activities

Treatment with total benzene extract of *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* flowers revealed antiestrogenic activity in bilaterally ovariectomized immature albino rats. It disrupted the estrous cycle in rats in a dose-duration dependent manner. The extract treatment led to a reduction in the weights of the ovary, uterus and pituitary. Ovaries showed follicular atresia, while uterus showed atrophic histological alterations. The effects reversed 30 days after the withdrawal of the extract treatment. In guinea pigs, on the other hand, the benzene and ethanolic extracts of the flowers produced an increase in the ovarian weight, and in the weight and diameter of the corpora lutea, indicating an estrogenic activity. The benzene extract administered orally to ovariectomized rats was active at 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 mg/kg body weight, while 95% ethanolic extract of the flowers was inactive at 100 mg/kg body weight and active at 150, 200 and 250 mg/kg body weight [10] causing significant decrease in ovarian, uterine and pituitary weights [11]. In another study, ethanol/water (1:1) extract administered at 75 mg/kg body weight led to reduction in glycogen content in uterus of treated animals showing antiestrogenic activity [12]. Benzene extract of the flowers, administered intraperitoneally to adult mice at 125 and 250 mg/kg body weight, resulted in an irregular estrous cycle with prolonged estrus and metestrus. Further, an increase in atretic follicles and the absence of corpora lutea indicated the antiovarian effect of the extract [13].

Anti-implantation activity

The benzene extract of *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers given orally at 100 mg/kg body weight caused postcoital antifertility effect in female albino rats with 80% reduction in the implantation site on 10th day of pregnancy. The petroleum ether extract was devoid of antifertility effect, whereas the ether and ethanolic extracts of the flower petals caused a change in the sex ratio of the pups born, female pups born being higher in the extract-treated rats. Benzene extract of the flower, administered orally at 50 and 250 mg/kg body weight during 1-4 of gestation, exerted anti-implantation effect without affecting the tubal transport of the zygote [14, 15]. The extract inhibited the hyperpermeability of endometrium capillaries which is the earliest known response of a receptive endometrium to any kind of decidual stimulus [16]. In another study, oral administration of the benzene extract of *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers at 1.0 g/kg body weight led to termination of pregnancy in about 92% of albino mice. The effect was associated with a significant fall in peripheral level of progesterone and increase in uterine acid phosphatase activity on day 10. The ovary exhibited signs of luteolysis, and the corpus luteal delta 5-3 beta -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase activity decreased markedly [17, 18]. In a study, ethanolic extract of roots of *H. rosa-sinensis* given orally to rats at 400 mg/kg body weight exhibited a very potent anti-implantation activity since no implants were observed in uteri at autopsy [19].

THERAPEUTIC EVALUATION

In a clinical trial, treatment of 21 women at reproductive age group with ethanolic extract of *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers at 750 mg/kg body weight/day in 3 doses, from 7th to 22nd day of menstrual cycle, 14 women did not have pregnancy for 4 years, whereas 7 women dropped out of the trial. The trials were also conducted with Vidangadi yoga (a herbal preparation containing *Embelia ribes* seeds, *H. rosa-sinensis* flowers and *Ferula foetida* oleo-gum resin) for antifertility activity and the drug was found to be quite effective without any harmful effects [20].

TOXICITY ASSESSMENT

Treatment with ethanol/water (1:1) extract of the aerial parts, administered intraperitoneally to both sexes of mice, produced LD₅₀ 1.0 g/kg [21].

CONCLUSION

It is obvious from the present article that not much work has been done to evaluate the contraceptive efficacy of *H. rosa-sinensis* in both males and females. Therefore, keeping in view the importance of *H. rosa-sinensis* in regulation of human fertility, there is an urgent need to undertake an extensive investigation for contraceptive potential of this plant so as to develop an orally active herbal contraceptive pill.

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